

Characteristics of Decade-bandwidth, Balanced Antipodal Vivaldi Antenna (BAVA) Phased Arrays with Time-Delay Beamformer Systems

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Abstract—The first part of this paper presents measured performance of the Balanced Antipodal Vivaldi Antenna (BAVA) with U-shaped metallic channels. This new BAVA array is dual polarized with decade bandwidth and wide scan volume. Its depth is half-wavelength at the highest frequency of operation. It can be constructed as modular individual BAVA elements or as a subarray with integrated transmitter / receiver (T/R) modules. This is a unique feature that reduces manufacturing complexity and the cost of field repair. The second part of this paper overviews performance of the BAVA array scanned at wide scan angles using AFRL’s Transformational Element Level Array (TELA) Time-Delay Units between 2 GHz to 8 GHz and using fixed delay lines between 2 GHz to 18 GHz. The authors offer guidelines for minimum aperture size to realize decade bandwidth beam scan performance without beam squinting at the lower end of the frequency band.

Keywords— Vivaldi; Balanced Antipodal Vivaldi Antenna; Electronically Scanned Arrays; True-time delay; Beamformer; Dual-Polarized; Cross-Polarization; Beam-squint.

I. INTRODUCTION

There are increasing demands to consolidate multiple narrowband antennas into a single wideband electronically scanned array (ESA). The goal is to provide more flexibility and functionality at reduced cost with consideration to limited space, light weight, and low power consumption requirements on modern small platforms. This requires advances in ESAs and their manufacturing technologies. This paper describes the characteristics of a novel radiating element that allows wideband operation and does not require special fabrication techniques.

Section II of this paper is devoted to an overview of other wideband ESA approaches and how they compare with the Balanced Antipodal Vivaldi Antenna (BAVA) array technology. Section III discusses BAVA array design and its performance. Section IV describes the performance of an 8×9 BAVA subarray between 2 GHz to 18 GHz at boresight and scanned up to ±45 degrees in azimuth. The main beam of the array squints at the lower end of the frequency band since the subarray is electrically small (i.e. from edge-to-edge is one-half

wavelength) at 2 GHz. To understand the cause of this beam squinting, the authors studied characteristics of the BAVA embedded element patterns for different array sizes and propose guidelines for future designs. Those guidelines are believed to be applicable to other wideband array technologies as well.

II. OVERVIEW OF WIDEBAND ESA TECHNOLOGIES

The following discussion lists existing decade or greater bandwidth ESA technologies and their pros and cons.

TABLE I. ASSESMENT OF BAVA VS. OTHER ESA TECHNOLOGIES WITH DECADE (10:1) BANDWIDTH OR MORE

Technology / Features	BAVA	Vivaldi	Interweaved Spiral	Long slots	Tightly coupled dipoles
Profile ^[a]	$\lambda_{Hi}/2$	$4 \lambda_{Hi}$	$\lambda_{Hi}/2$		
Polarization Agility ^[b]	SP, DP		CP only	SP	SP, DP
Scan volume ^[c]	±45°	±60°	Not reported	±60°	±60°
Cross polarization at 45° scan angle along diagonal plane	-17 dB	-5 dB	Not reported		-15 dB
Metallic backing	Yes			Yes, but needs special treatment	
Feed	Simple 50 Ω stripline		Gap source	Coax to vias with high aspect ratio, and need balun	
Modularity	Yes	No			

^a Total height from ground plane to the radiating aperture of the array.

^b SP: Single polarization, DP: Dual-linear polarization, CP: Circular polarization.

^c For an average active VSWR < 3 across entire 10:1 bandwidth.

An “Egg-crate” array of tapered-slot (Vivaldi) elements is capable of operating over $F_{Hi}/F_{Lo}=12:1$ bandwidth at wide scan-angles [1,2]. However, the elements are typically very long: more than $4\lambda_{Hi}$ in height, where λ_{Hi} is the free-space wavelength at the high end of the band [2]. They also suffer

from high cross-polarization when scanned in the diagonal plane [3], degrading the array's polarization purity. In addition, they are not amenable to modular construction [4].

A planar, interweaved spiral array was recently introduced exhibiting nearly 10:1 bandwidth at boresight for a circularly polarized array only [5]. Since the radiating element is a two-arm spiral, dual-linear polarization is not possible. Note this simulated result was achieved using gap-source excitation in a computer. This implies challenges in the realization of the array due to difficulties in incorporating wideband feed/balun.

Single polarized conjugate long slot (connected magnetic dipoles) arrays demonstrated 10:1 bandwidth with superior scan-impedance performance [6]. However, they require dispersive ferro-electric substrate loading to mitigate reflection from the array's ground plane backing. The dual-polarized "Thumbtack" version of this array is limited to 3:1 bandwidth only [7].

Variations of tightly-coupled printed dipoles [8-11] have utilized a concept similar to Prof. Ben Munk's current sheet antenna (CSA) [12]. They offer substantial size, weight, and volume saving with superior bandwidth. However, they come with penalties. Those arrays require stringent dimensional tolerances for element-to-element coupling, fabrication challenges incorporating high aspect ratio plated vias, and expensive processes to form cavities in the printed wiring board (PWB) to suppress surface-waves.

III. BALANCED ANTIPODAL VALDADI ANTENNA (BAVA)

BAVA was first introduced in 1996, but was limited to a small, single row, linear array providing 3:1 bandwidth [13]. In 2008, Elsallal and Schaubert demonstrated a 5:1 bandwidth performance in planar BAVA array that scans up to $\pm 60^\circ$ [14]. In 2011, Elsallal and Mather introduced a new design approach for the BAVA, Fig. 1. By inserting U-shaped metallic channels between adjoining elements, the BAVA's bandwidth increased to 10:1 [15]. Those channels increase inter-element capacitive coupling between the radiator tips. Note the U-channels do not make electrical contact with the radiating elements.

Fig. 1. Structure of decade bandwidth BAVA array. [a] Notional sketch of dual polarized BAVA unit cell. Element spacing along E- and H- plane, and element height equal to $\lambda_{HI}/2$ [b] Modular construction of the BAVA.

Fig. 2 depicts the embedded element gain of the BAVA array from infinite array simulation in HFSS [16], from two different finite array simulations in CST [17], and DD-FEM [18] between 2 GHz to 18 GHz. The simulated results agree well with measured performance of the 8x9 BAVA subarray at boresight. On average, there is no more than -2 dB loss in embedded element gain when compared to the theoretical gain limit ($4\pi \times \text{Area} / \lambda^2$) at boresight. Note the central element is fed by 50 Ω striplines and coaxial connectors. No wideband impedance matching network or special mitigation to the ground plane are needed.

Fig. 2. Embedded element gain of different BAVA array sizes (Infinite x Infinite, 66x66, 55x10 and 8x9) at boresight.

Fig. 3 shows the simulated active VSWR performance of the BAVA array at broadside and for wide angle scanning up to $\pm 45^\circ$ in the three primary planes. The average VSWR is less than 2.5 broadside and along the E- and D- planes. However, the average active VSWR < 3.5 when the BAVA array is scanned in the H-plane. Reduced scan impedance in the H-plane is a typical performance for Vivaldi type arrays. There is ongoing research to improve this performance.

Fig. 3. Active VSWR of the BAVA array.

Fig. 4 shows a composite plot of the embedded element patterns in the E-, D- and H- plane cuts, with Co- and Cross (Cx)- polarizations superimposed in the same graph for comparison. The arrow on the aperture shows the E-field orientation of the incident wave in the anechoic chamber. Overall, the Co-polarized patterns (solid lines) follow a curve that is better than the $(\cos\theta)^{1.35}$ roll-off. The Cx-polarization (dashed lines) is better than -25 dB in the principal planes. The BAVA also has a very unique feature: the Cx-polarization is

less than -17 dB in the diagonal plane scanning at 45° across the entire frequency band. This provides excellent isolation for high performance, wide scan, dual linearly or circularly polarized arrays.

Fig. 4. Array measurement. [a] Coordinate system and definition of the BAVA's E-plane polarization. [b] Embedded element patterns in the E-, D- and H- plane cuts, with Co-pol (solid) and Cx-pol (dashed) superimposed, for scan volumes ranges between $\pm 67.5^\circ$, from 2 GHz to 18 GHz.

IV. BAVA ARRAY AND TIME DELAY BEAMFORMER

The AFRL team has developed an 8-bit time delay unit (TDU) that operates between 0.8 GHz and 8 GHz for the Transformational Element Level Array (TELA) test bed [19]. Rockwell Collins integrated the TELA TDU modules and their digital control lines on a compact size eight-way combiner, shown in Fig. 5. The average error in differential group delay between the channels is less than 10 psec, which is fairly flat across the entire frequency range.

Fig. 5. Performance of the integrated TDU with 8-way combiner. [a] Description of key components. [b] Group delay bit as a function of frequency.

The integrated circuit was connected to eight BAVA elements in the center of the 8×9 dual polarized subarray. All other BAVA elements were terminated with 50Ω loads. An Arduino kit powered via USB port was programmed and used to control the delay bits and amplitude taper via Matlab and intranet web interface; see Fig. 6. The setup was measured inside an anechoic chamber.

Fig. 6. Arduino setup to control the beamformer.

Fig. 7 shows the measured radiation patterns for this setup at boresight and scanning $\pm 45^\circ$ in the array E-plane (azimuth) across the TELA's bandwidth (2 GHz - 8 GHz). It is noteworthy that although the BAVA flared fins are asymmetric (Fig. 1a), the beams steered between $\pm 45^\circ$ are symmetric.

Fig. 7. Measured normalized radiation patterns of the 8x9 BAVA subarray with TELA modules between 2 GHz and 8 GHz. Note the BAVA array's low frequency cut-off is 2 GHz. The TELA's high frequency cut-off is 8 GHz. [a] Boresight. [b] Scanning at 45° . [c] Sweeping the main beam between $\pm 45^\circ$ at 8 GHz.

Since the AFRL TELA beamformer has an upper frequency cut off at 8 GHz, fixed-length coaxial cables were used to demonstrate wide angle scanning at $\pm 45^\circ$ over the entire frequency bandwidth of the BAVA array, i.e. 2 GHz - 18 GHz. Simulations of the same subarray size, but with ideal time delay excitations, are shown in Figure 8 for comparison.

Fig. 8. Normalized radiation patterns of the 8x9 BAVA subarray with fixed length coaxial delay line. [a] Theoretical patterns (ideal excitation, i.e. with no cable losses or lengths mismatch). [b] Measured patterns.

The above tests establish a high simulation to measurement correlation and show squint-free beam scanning for arrays operating above 4 GHz.

The beam squint below 4 GHz is due to the size of the 8x9 BAVA subarray. It is too small electrically (edge-to-edge length is $\lambda/2$ at 2 GHz). The center element therefore does not see an infinite array environment. In other words, it encounters substantial reflection from the array edges.

To prove this hypothesis, different BAVA array sizes were simulated, and compared to the ideal theoretical gain limit. The E- and H- plane cut of the embedded element patterns, shown in Fig. 9 - 10, were examined in the field of view -90° to 0° over the entire 2 GHz - 18 GHz. The patterns were calculated from the theta- and phi- components of the simulated farfield transformed to the "Ludwig 3" representation using the below equations. The finite array analysis was conducted in MWS CST [17] for the 8x9 and 17x18 elements. The DD-FEM was used to simulate the 66x66 element array [18].

$$E = E_\theta \cos \phi - E_\phi \sin \phi \quad (1)$$

$$P = \frac{1}{Z_o} \int_0^\pi \int_0^{2\pi} |E|^2 \sin \vartheta \, d\vartheta \, d\varphi, \quad \text{where } Z_o = \sqrt{\frac{\mu}{\epsilon}} \quad (2)$$

[a]

[b]

[c]

Fig. 9. Embedded element pattern as a function of array size for 2 GHz to 6 GHz in 2 GHz steps. Absolute value of the farfields patterns are plotted in half of the field view only for clarity.

[a]

[b]

[c]

Fig. 10. Embedded element pattern as a function of array size for 8 GHz to 12 GHz in 2 GHz steps. Patterns for frequencies above 12 GHz are not plotted because the oscillations stopped. Absolute value of the farfields patterns are plotted in half of the field view only for clarity.

Previous simulations have validated that a 66×66 BAVA array is sufficiently large to represent an infinite array environment [20]. The 66×66 BAVA array is used herein for E- or H- plane beam scan performance prediction. The following observations can be made. (1) At low frequency bands, embedded element patterns have oscillations due to scattering from the array's edges. (2) When the array size exceeds 2.67λ in the E-plane and 1.3λ in the H-plane at the lowest frequency of operation, the embedded element pattern becomes smoother, and resembles the behavior seen in a large array. This ensures squint-free beam scanning across the entire frequency band of the array.

To explain why the E-plane dimension of the BAVA array is larger than that the H-plane dimension, the mutual coupling between the center and edge BAVA elements was examined. The mutual coupling between elements along the E-plane is found to be greater than those along H-plane of the array. Since the oscillations are less severe in the H-plane pattern, we conclude that the reflection from the edges in the H-plane is less due to the reduced mutual coupling. This is generally accepted as valid observations for many ultra-wideband arrays [20].

A larger BAVA array is currently being built to demonstrate squint-free operation across the entire band using time-delay beamformers.

V. CONCLUSION

An 8×9 BAVA subarray was connected to an ultra-wide band beamformer, featuring the TELA integrated circuit TDU, for a first-time demonstration of a dual polarized electronically scanned array (ESA) operating over a decade (10:1) bandwidth. The aperture height is only one half-wavelength ($\lambda/2$) at the highest frequency of operation and supports beam scanning to 45° . This is an enabling technology for new applications of ISR platforms.

This paper also provides guidance relative to the size requirement for a 10:1 bandwidth BAVA phased array. For scanning in one dimension, the array size should exceed 2.67λ along the E-plane, and 1.33λ along the H-plane at the lowest operating frequency. If the application requires scanning in both dimensions, the array should be at least 2.67λ in each dimension at the lowest operating frequency.

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